

Multi-actor collaboration dynamics and capacity building network inside and between AKIS to foster the upscaling of SFSCs across Europe

Deliverable 2.1

Set up minimum requirements and criteria for inclusion (M1-M12)

Responsible partner: KIS

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Table 1 History of changes

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1 Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Information Systems The Agricultural knowledge and information system (AKIS) links and integrates farmers, researchers, agricultural educationists, extensionists and encourages them to exploit and promote reciprocated learning and to create, share, and make use of agriculture-related technology, knowledge and information. Farmer communities are at the centre of the knowledge triangle created. The AKIS concept recognizes that research is not the only means of generating or gaining access to knowledge. Although the AKIS also focuses on research supply, it gives much consideration to the links among the knowledge actors and the recognition of farmers' demand.
AKIS integration process	The Member States in the framework of the AKIS can set-up their SFSC advisory system based on a recommended selection criteria for SFSC advisors which comes from the EU4ADVICE project
BAS	Business Advisory System
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CSA	Community Supported Agriculture
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
ISS	Innovation Support Service
KIS	Kislépték Association
LAG	Local Action Group
LL	Living Lab
MS	Member State
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
SFSC	Short food supply chain
SWG	Strategic Working Group
RDP	Rural Development Programme

2 Executive Summary

The aim of this report is to find minimum criteria, characteristics of Short Food Supply Chain (SFSC) advisors and to recommend a checklist for those who give advice for SFSC actors. The overall objective of recommending such a selection criteria framework for SFSC advisors is to support the integration into the EU SFSC Knowledge Transfer Network and of prerequisites for advisory services to be integrated into national AKIS and comply with national CAP Strategic Plans. **Each country has a different background and SFSC ecosystem thus the established checklist of core requirements for the SFSC advisors is only a recommendation, a guideline** which can be used by the Member States (MSs) for the integration into their National AKIS.

As an **overall SFSC advisory criteria system does not exist yet in Europe and in most European Union MSs**, and the available CAP Strategic Plans do not yet include a framework for SFSC advisory services, a bottom-up approach is recommended to apply for measuring the proper needs of local stakeholders.

The leading factor of defining the characteristics of SFSC advisors' profile is that **SFSC is still an ideological concern thus such a criteria system cannot be completely objective, measurable and applied for every country**. The main gap is how MSs or the EU identify the actors of SFSC and what kind of supporting environment (policy, institutions, organisations) is placed at the disposal of these actors.

Another determinant is many actors already operates **as informal SFSC advisors** (such as mentors, coaches, farmers' market organisers, facilitators, consultants, mediators, researchers, farmers, consumers, tourism agents, local action groups, communication agents, etc.). These actors are often invisible, hence their concrete actions and characteristics are hardly measurable or objectified, and the further evaluation is particularly exacerbated by the hidden actors of SFSC (farmers, not registered farmers, not registered supporting communities, consumers' communities, informal farmers' collaborations).

The main topics that can support the identification of SFSC advisors are:

- field and level of education,
- field of advice,
- references,
- the target group,
- competencies,
- skills,
- organisational background,
- way of giving advice,

which topics are listed with subtopics in Table 3. Many of these are **already in line with the current AKISs which facilitate the integration process (T2.3)**. Those characteristics which are quite specific for SFSC, such as target groups and skills should be considered through the further steps.

Concerning the integration of SFSC advisors into AKIS it shall be highlighted that the new CAP requires the MSs to offer advice on each of the three sustainability pillars and "to make advisors more competent, the **CAP asks for integration of all impartial advisors within the AKIS, in particular the most trusted ones who have a major impact on the ground**". It has been settled in our research that the **SFSC advisors can be defined as those actors who are trusted in a certain territory or a local community**. This is a criterion that is difficult to measure but should be somehow included in a checklist of recommended criteria.

At the current phase of the project our goal is to get all the formal and informal advisors on board. There is one important prerequisite for the criteria of a European SFSC knowledge network: we need consultants who

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are willing to share (WP5) their knowledge, experience and questions at EU level to create an interactive EU network and platform.

The recommendation will be provided for the Living Labs to use, examine and give feedback on what the engaged stakeholders think about this checklist, and how it should be modified based on their experience and knowledge. During the project this checklist can be shortened or completed by results in the four LLs. The LL workshops can provide additional information for the development of the checklist and can contribute to the clarification and validation.

This paper may provide a basis for networking activities including thematic workshops, Living Lab meetings and cross-visits to connect SFSC-advisors of the 27 MSs of the EU, to foster sharing best practices, peer-to-peer learning, cooperation, and cross-fertilization. Moreover, the results will be integrated into the contents and tools for SFSC capacity building (WP3) and will provide recommendations for the integration of SFSC advisors into national AKIS in EU (T2.3).

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3 Introduction

Work Package 2 aims to support the Specific Objective 1 (SO1) together with the WP1 to identify and characterise the SFSC advisors across Europe. Under **Task 2.1 defining the minimum requirements including competencies, skills, knowledge, education, and even the target groups could serve as a recommendation, guideline of the characterization**. To be in line with the CAP post-2020, AKIS advisors should cover a wider variety of topics, beyond agronomical and technical aspects, including economic, legal, environmental, business, digitalization and technology issues. The typical definition and profile of the advisor, which varies according to the countries, shall be reviewed and extended, taking into account CAP requirements, in order to include a broader scope of skills and knowledge that effectively address the current challenges faced by farmers and food producers. In our research we put great emphasis on these requirements thus the different topics cover business knowledge, digitalization, IT, etc.

3.1 Aim of the task

The purpose of this task is to recommend a set of basic requirements and criteria for an advisor to be called and identified as an SFSC-specific advisor and on how it is possible to distinguish SFSC advisory from other agricultural extension services. It would give recommendations on based on what requirements an SFSC advisor could operate on the field in practice and on what basis the consortiums can establish the European SFSC Knowledge Transfer Network.

So a preliminary check list of selection criteria for SFSC advisors is recommended to serve as a basis for the participation in the EU network, and of prerequisites for advisory services to be integrated into national AKIS and comply with national CAP Strategic Plans, to include a wide diversity of advisor profiles.

For common understanding a workshop was organized during the kick-off meeting of EU4ADVICE where partners detailed the important objectives to be reached in the task:

1. to define the areas which determine the work field of advisors and see who can be called and operate in practice as an advisor in the field of short food supply chains.
2. to define who is out of the circle, and who should not be included in it. It should be clarified which advisors and actors can not be called SFSC advisors, this is relevant because of the policy supports, eligibility criteria, and pure SFSC-focused subsidies.

An urgent challenge is that the target groups of the SFSCs can hardly receive the necessary information and the required knowledge is not mainstream. There are a lot of niche products on the market, a lot of innovation practices, specific regulations and solutions that require the development of non-existent methodologies. Actually, more informal advisors, mentors, SFSC market organisers, and knowledge providers support farmers and food producers whose operation may provide appropriate information for further examination and definition of minimum requirements.

The recommended checklist is established based on a methodology created by Kislépték Association (KIS) - which includes a Questionnaire and Focus Group Discussion guide - considering all the differences and similarities among the MSs coming from the received feedback of different partners and stakeholders in each country in the Questionnaire and during the Focus Group Discussions under the facilitation and guidance of KIS. The recommended checklist could be validated by the SWG SCAR-AKIS and SWG Food Systems and the document will be reviewed and maintained in collaboration with a sister project COREnet funded under HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-27

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3.2 Related Specific Objectives

WP2 is connected to the listed Specific Objectives (SO):

SO1 – Identify and characterize SFSC advisors across Europe (WP1 and 2): Drawing on existing inventories of SFSC advisors, an updated list of SFSC advisors from all MSs will be created. According to CAP post-2020, AKIS advisors should now cover a wider variety of topics, beyond agronomical and technical aspects, including economic, legal, environmental, business, digitalisation, and technological issues. ***The typical definition and profile of the advisor, which varies according to the countries, shall thus be reviewed and extended, taking into account CAP requirements, to include a broader scope of skills and knowledge that effectively address the current challenges faced by farmers and food producers.***

SO3 – Improve the understanding of the main issues and challenges of European AKIS (WP1 and 2): There are significant differences between the national AKIS across MSs, in terms of the level of integration and advisory power. Each country is facing its own challenges in the process of structuring the AKIS, according to its political, socioeconomic, cultural, and sociological background. ***Understanding these issues, as well as the key success and hindering factors, is a key step towards the integration of SFSC advisors within national AKIS. In this sense, capitalizing on the findings of previous projects (i2connect, PROAKIS, etc.) and collaborating with new ones (GOVERNANCE-01-25), information on the structure of AKIS and the role of advisors in the different MSs will be compiled.*** As the information provided by these projects covers general advisory services, the analysis of the presence of SFSC topics in MS AKIS will be performed to detect the main barriers and opportunities for the integration of SFSC issues.

SO4 – Integrate SFSC advisors and contents into national AKIS (WP2 and 3): The establishment of SFSCs-specific supporting services and sharing of materials will be implemented at living lab (LL) level as pilot activities with potential to be cooperatively up-scaled in different MS. Building on the outcomes of the previous workshops, focus groups, and projects related to SFSCs, a series of guidelines about SFSC-specific contents will be disseminated in the requested formats through EU networks and AKIS channels, ready for their adaptation and translation to specific contexts. ***These guidelines shall cover all the dimensions of advice needed by SFSC actors, such as business models, marketing, carbon and environmental issues, technological and non-technological solutions for processing, packaging, logistics and sales, consumer demand, etc.***

SO5 – Interact with relevant national/regional/local policy-makers (WP 2 and 4): According to its multi-actor approach, EU4Advice also aims at creating interactions between local, regional, national, and EU policymakers in order to involve them in the process of integrating SFSC advisors into AKIS, but also to tackle the most important regulatory barriers to the development of SFSCs. ***The project will explore the policies, legal and regulatory requirements for successful SFSCs, taking into account the different national and regional contexts, in a co-creative approach involving policy makers, advisors, and producers at different administrative levels.*** Capitalising on the policy recommendations and roadmap produced in former projects (SMARTCHAIN, Strength2food, etc.), the objective is to provide feedback from the EU network of SFSC advisors to relevant policymakers about SFSC issues, sharing with them their most important needs in terms of regulation and support.

In general, T2.1 will contribute to reaching SO1, SO3, SO4, SO5 by providing a better understanding of who could be the SFSC advisors, and how the different Member States define their SFSC-related advisory

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services. This task was accomplished in the first year of the project, when the AKISs, the new criteria systems and related policies had not been established in all the MS, thus a complex in-depth analysis of the whole EU level system is not possible at this moment.

3.3 Compilation with National CAP Strategic Plans

The list of selection criteria should comply with National CAP Strategic Plans in order to include a wide diversity of advisor profiles. In the summary overview of the CAP plans for the 27 MSs knowledge sharing, innovation, and digitalisation are mentioned as tools that can help reach all CAP-specific objectives. The aim is to achieve the transition to more resilient and sustainable rural areas¹. It has been settled that increased efforts in advice, coaching, training, and other knowledge exchange actions are necessary. The strengthening of the AKIS thus should be used to boost knowledge exchange and networking, and advisors must be named as key actors in this process. In line with the aims of the EU4ADVICE project, the importance of networking even with experts from abroad can be highlighted, as the SFSC advisory network under establishment is supporting the knowledge exchange aspiration. The new CAP requires the MSs to offer advice on each of the three sustainability pillars and “to make advisors more competent, **the CAP asks for integration of all impartial advisors within the AKIS, in particular the most trusted ones who have a major impact on the ground**”. It has been identified during our research that the SFSC advisors can be defined as those actors who are trusted in a certain territory or among a local community and this is such a criteria that is hardly measurable or could be included in a kind of checklist of criteria.

The role of the AKIS coordination bodies and the national CAP Networks involves setting up platforms providing farmers and advisors with knowledge and information and connecting farmers, advisors, researchers, and others. Throughout the whole national CAP summary document, the essential role of advisors and the importance of knowledge sharing, exchange, and networking prove the need for developing the circumstances of the advisory systems. **The SFSC-specific extension services/advisory is not highlighted but the importance of knowledge in the field of sustainable agriculture and food system transformation is a key element, which covers the role and characteristics of SFSC advice.**

All in all, it can be concluded that **compliance with the National CAP Strategic Plans in the case of the criteria system is something that would require more information about the plans of each country on the short food supply chain related issues which are currently not available.** However, the necessity of developing an SFSC-focused advisory system clearly lies in the strong emphasis (as an example in the case of Hungary and the Netherlands) of local markets, the development of digital opportunities such as shopping communities, and online marketing. All the farmers, and organisations who will take part in the development of short supply chains, establishing local food systems, quality schemes, etc. will strongly need specific support in terms of knowledge and information, and this support should come from advisors specialised in short food supply chains.

¹ European Commission: Approved 28 CAP Strategic Plans (2023-2027) Summary overview for 27 Member States, Facts and figures <https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-06/approved-28-cap-strategic-plans-2023-27.pdf>

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4 Methodology and Tools

Based on the above-mentioned objectives and initiating experiences, KIS developed a methodology that supports the investigation of the minimum requirements for SFSC advisors. The methodology is based on the practical experience of KIS with SFSC advisors/managers as being an advisory group/organization, which provide advice and training for the actors of SFSCs.

4.1 Background and Justification

Our hypothesis was the following at the beginning:

- Farm advisory system gives advice and solutions but at the level of SFSCs there are a lot of uncovered knowledge and information gaps;
- Goal of the establishment of a new SFSC advisory system is to fill these gaps to create a better operating SFSC;
- The challenges and questions in the SFSCs are unique, territory and/or actor specific in most of the cases thus there is no one-size-fits-all solution;
- A recommended core list of criteria is needed that can be adapted to the SFSC Knowledge Advisory System.

The theoretical background is ensured by the i2Connect Deliverable 1.1, the EU4Advice Deliverable 1.1, and the SMARTCHAIN Horizon2020 project results D9.5 Roadmap towards the adaptation of the EU regulatory framework to SFSCs.

As a starting point we applied the main thesis of Knierim et al., (2020) and we assumed that the SFSC advisors converge towards the “innovation advisor”. For better understanding, the team of KIS prepared a figure (Figure 1) about the complexity of the relevant fields and attributions of SFSC advisory activities which determine the framework of the SFSC specific advice. This figure defines those 4 core aspects/topics of the expected requirements which can demonstrate the minimum criteria for the SFSC advisors to be able to provide appropriate knowledge:

- field of advice;
- education field and level of the advisor;
- target groups of the advisory activity;
- competencies and skills of the advisors.

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The possible areas of minimum requirements for Short Food Supply Chain advisors

Figure 1: Possible areas of minimum requirements for SFSC advisors. Source: own figure

The D9.5 Roadmap towards the adaptation of the EU regulatory framework to SFSCs (Méhauden, 2021, p. 50) shows that capacity building in SFSCs is a key point. The first path that requires further dedication is the transfer of all the knowledge created within the project to practitioners, and in other sister projects such as Strength2food and SKIN, through the development, demonstration and dissemination of ready-to-use solutions and models (guides and tools), based on detailed and quantified data.

The i2Connect Deliverable 1.1 Innovation advisors for interactive innovation process: Conceptual grounds and common understandings defined the typology of requested competencies of innovation advisors. Authors (Knierim et al. 2020) emphasised that the roles of an advisor are diverse, reflecting the changing perspectives on an extension over the last few decades and it became a “multi-faceted, multi-purpose, multi-scaled and multi-disciplinary field” (Ampt et al. 2015). To be able to answer complex questions advisors need to gain the following competencies (Figure 2):

1. Basic disposition + attitude: This forms the foundation and refers to the need for an understanding of “extension” and advisory work, which in the Hohenheim philosophy of advisory work is supported in problem-solving. The advisor must not only understand this but also accept the role and responsibilities in the advisory process. In terms of attitudes, congruency, empathy, and appreciation are the three basic attitudes that lay the groundwork for any relationship between an advisor and the client.

2. Content competence: The advisor must be credible and knowledgeable in the subject matter and have the ability to link it to the context of the farming and family system as well as the whole context of the client’s livelihood.

3. Methodological competence: Communication skills (including individual advisory talks, group facilitation and training, handling large group events, etc.), and diagnostic and analytical skills that include the ability to interpret the verbal and nonverbal behaviour of people in order to gain an empathetic understanding and

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guide a fruitful dialogue. Knowledge about selecting and applying concepts that support the entire problem-solving process from diagnosis to evaluation including the socio-psychological aspects.

4. Managerial and organisational competence: the ability of advisors to avoid getting into role conflicts where the advisor is free from his/her own or external interests and has no hierarchical relationship with the client. Also important is to be competent in an organisational setup that will establish a positive framework within which the advisor can facilitate the work and give the necessary guidance and backstopping.

5. Reflection, learning & personal development: a good advisor should constantly reflect on his /her work, proactively seek feedback, and when necessary, consult others when he/she has difficulties. The advisor should also engage in life-long learning to update technological and methodological knowledge and skills.

Figure 2: Qualification of an advisor. Source: Hoffmann et al. (2009), cited Knierim et al. (2020)

All the areas are paired with dedicated sections in the Questionnaire (Annex 3). The aim was to discover the situation, and the existing circumstances of the SFSC-related advisory system (if it exists) in each partner country based on the expertise of the relevant professionals.

4.1.1 Workshop at the kick-off meeting

At the EU4Advice kick-off meeting (Amsterdam, 5-7 October 2022) a special workshop was organised to initiate the first discussion of the consortium partners on the most delicate issues: what is SFSC, who are SFSC advisors and what are the minimum expected criteria.

A main concern was how the experts would define the SFSC advisors and those advisors who can not be identified in the field of SFSC. Other questions raised: How is it possible to distinguish the SFSC advisory services from other agricultural extension services? How will an SFSC advisor operate in the fields? The main objective of these discussions was to map the experts' different approaches and to observe the expected, required experience which may not include all the possible SFSC advisors. 45 experts participated at the workshop, spending 20-20 minutes at three tables where they had discussions based on the following questions:

- 1st round: The main questions discussed by the experts during the first round were: What are the main criteria of being an SFSC advisor? Where does the work of an SFSC advisor start?

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- 2nd round: In the second round the experts raised the question of how we can define the SFSC advisory services and criteria, and which organization must be involved in the different countries. How should the process of SFSC system building be launched?
- 3rd round: In this group, the main topic of the discussion expanded the minimum expectable experience from SFSC advisors.

The outcomes of the discussions are listed in Annex 1.

4.1.2 Competence matrix of the Rural Facilitator Erasmus+ KA2 project

The Rural Facilitator project² was funded by the European Commission's Erasmus + programme. The project started in November 2019 and lasted for 2 years, until 2022. The main aim of the project was to explore the possible ways in CZ, HU, RO, PL, and FR to generate the position of a so-called rural facilitator and to develop the necessary learning materials and training tools. A transnational survey was conducted to help better understand what competencies/ skills / and knowledge the desired SFSC facilitator role should possess. The final training material and curricula were the main outcome of the projects which were elaborated based on the collected knowledge and competence needs.

Based on qualitative and quantitative data, the analysis unveiled key common shared opinions and differences between the countries. Each nation had its own hierarchy of the listed skills, competencies, and knowledge; however, the commonalities weigh much more than the given differences. The most important knowledge and competencies were:

- Leadership skills: the facilitator can act as a coach, who can motivate and inspire actors in the rural area to achieve a common vision. Interpersonal skills are a big part of the leader's toolkit, as they are continuously engaged with people.
- Knowledge of SFSCs: for the facilitators to be an effective asset for the short food supply chains, they must possess prior knowledge of the operation of SFSCs.
- Food hygiene: food hygiene has received eminent importance in every nation's sample. Such knowledge is indispensable for the facilitator to see through several processes regarding SFSCs for him/her to be able to recognize flaws within the chains, and to be able to effectively deal with them.
- Communication: being able to compromise and manage conflicts, and coming up with win-win solutions is as much of a question of communication as of leadership itself.
- Marketing knowledge: Even if marketing is a part of the business skills, increased focus should be administered on this topic. Marketing is a topic complex enough to be represented in a separate module. Both traditional and online marketing elements could prove beneficial for the SFSC.

In developing the T2.1 Questionnaire, the concept and some of the questions were formulated taking into account the experience gained from the evaluation of the Rural Facilitator questionnaire.

4.1.3 Minimum criteria to map advisors in D1.1

Deliverable 1.1 listed the advisors in the common EU4Advice and COREnet database in order to include those who exceed the typical definition and profile of a standard agricultural advisor, which varies according to the countries and represents those with a broader scope of skills and knowledge that effectively address the current challenges faced by farmers and food producers. A multi-step approach was designed to map the available advisors. A set of minimum criteria for SFSC advisors was developed to ensure consistency and

² <https://www.ruralfacilitator.eu/en/> Project reference number: 2019-1-CZ01-KA202-061270

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quality across the countries. ***By examination of the minimum criteria system, the D1.1 was used as a basis to build the results on the ongoing mapping task.***

The D1.1 applied the output of the i2connect project³ which was collecting the required competencies and practical knowledge of an innovation advisor in the field of agriculture. This output is in line with the objective of this Task. They investigated the possible competencies in 5 areas and created a competence diagram at an individual level (see Session 4.1). Which is different from the methodology used in the framework of this deliverable.

All in all, the competence diagram created in the framework of the i2connect project provided a basis for the development of the methodology, ***as the different areas and their subcategories could be adapted to the circumstances of the SFSC advisors.*** The SFSC-specific context of the AKIS was investigated in MSs based on the i2connect AKIS country reports in the framework of Task 1.1. Thus, we used the outcomes as a kind of base and background information for the criteria system.

4.2 Questionnaire

Based on more initial discussions with Task partners a Questionnaire was prepared to map the situation in the EU countries on the field of minimum criteria of SFSC advisors, if any. We knew that in most countries, there is no such definition of short food supply chain advisors, but aimed to find those minimum criteria that are important to be required from someone who wants to give proper advice. We suggested to the partners if they did not have an SFSC advisory system in their country yet then try to answer the questions based on what SFSC actors (for example farmers, producers, local governments, HoReCa sector actors, etc.) would need in terms of knowledge. This inverse logic supported us in finding the characteristics of the ideal advisor by understanding the local needs of the target groups.

Through the Questionnaire the necessary competencies, skills, and available SFSC-related training (which based on the outcomes of the evaluation Focus Group Discussions should be further examined in EU countries in the framework of the project) were aimed to be discovered. Based on the shared information it could become possible to filter who and under what conditions can be called a SFSC consultant. In addition to the creation of the criteria system, a secondary goal was to add ammunition to the didactical tool being prepared in Work Package 3, in which directions need to be developed at the EU and national level, and the third goal is to nourish the policy brief and the implementation of the AKIS.

The answers were received from 14 European countries counting 22 responses at all. Those who provided their answers were from different organizations such as partners of the EU4ADVICE and COREnet projects, and other experts on the field of SFSCs in other European countries (for example from Croatia) (demonstrated on Figure 3).

4.3 Online Evaluation Focus Groups

After receiving all the answers, the KIS team developed a methodology for evaluating the outcomes with an EU-wide technical expert group invited from EU4Advice, COREnet projects, and third parties in the framework of online Focus Group Discussions where the outcomes of the Questionnaire and the possible minimum criteria, the linkages between the projects, other work packages and the possible next steps were discussed.

³ <https://i2connect-h2020.eu/>

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Two rounds of Focus Group Discussions were organized through the TEAMS platform due to the number of invited experts and their availability. The invitations were based on the expertise in the field of the SFSC ecosystem and insights on the needs of the SFSC stakeholders, producers, organizers etc., and on the knowledge, and information they have access to. On the first occasion 13 experts and at the second occasion 8 participants attended besides the team of KIS (ANNEX 5 participants list). Both events started with an overview presentation of the Questionnaire outcomes and continued with the discussion based on guiding questions moderated by KIS.

Figure 3.: Countries covered: Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Poland, Romania, Spain, Sweden, The Netherlands, United Kingdom. Source: own edition

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5 Analyses of setting up the criteria system

5.1 Kick-off meeting - workshop on the criteria - who is in who is out of the SFSC advisory network

The experts drawn two types of approaches during the discussions

- a) value chain approach
 - b) networking approach
- a) Those who emphasised the value chain approach believe that SFSC advisors should understand and have a strong overview on each step of the chain. They must see what kind of input material providers determine the first phase of the short value chain and who supports farmers to reach consumers at the end. These experts think that SFSC advisors do not need to have special knowledge in each step, however, they must understand the process, and must understand how the local food chains work at local levels. These advisors can support the negotiations between the stakeholders, encourage cooperation, and see how to find solutions for gaps in each phase of the chain. One of the most debated issues was where the short chain starts and at which point the advisors shall come into action. Most of the participants agreed that the task of the advisor starts from the ready-to-use/ready-to-sell products and not from the primary production. One said it depends on the chains because a CSA action can start at the primary production as the farmers must learn how to plan a year in a greenhouse. It was a small sticking point because some of them agreed that for these questions we have a well-organized advisory system. While in some countries the main issue is how they can arrange the CSA processes, plant protection, nutrient management, etc. topics that are not relevant from our point of view.
- b) The second group of experts expressed that SFSC advisors are more like innovation brokers, networking people whose main task is communication, marketing and to act as a connecting counterpart at territory level. Someone who knows all the stakeholders and is able to organize matchmaking events. Based on the discussion one of the main criteria of the SFSC advisory system is to be transparent and be able to answer the who, where and why questions. The current SFSC advisors' work is based on trust. They agreed that more NGOs work with SFSC groups as informal advisors. They help them and trust them for a long time, which can serve as the basis for new networks, and platforms. The partners shall map these NGOs and involve them in the network. Among the partners it should be an agreement that the trust-based knowledge transfer systems work as local best practices.

5.2 Available SFSC advisor/manager training, education, and requirements in the European Union member states based on T1.1

In the framework of Task 1.1 19 countries were covered with information about the AKIS concerning SFSC. One of the questions was about the recognition of SFSC advisors and certification, and on the knowledge transfer methods, education specifically on SFSCs.

Investigating all the 19 cases for 18 countries the official or formal recognition does not exist in the case of SFSC advisors. Those who do SFSC-related counselling, mentoring, and advisory services belong to and are implemented by local organizations, non-governmental initiatives or even based on a consumer level. If there is no official recognition then specific, minimum requirements, even in the level or field of education, SFSC advisors do not exist yet in the countries. The knowledge transfers for SFSC advisors, stakeholders in most cases are also provided by local organizations and even managed by the SFSC managers, operators, and groups by themselves through social media or other online platforms. The systems are operated autonomously, and most of the SFSC innovations, local food initiatives are in the civil sector. Based on the reports it can be concluded that in some countries there are steps or planned steps taken to the development

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of creating a formal framework, but yet the current circumstances could not serve as a basis for setting up minimum criteria for SFSC advisors.

In the case of the Netherlands “farmers are able to get a subsidy (SABE) if they want to learn and make changes towards more sustainable agriculture. However, in order to get this subsidy, they must make use of a certified advisor. Certified advisors are stated in the BAS register. (Business Advisory System). For a farmer to get SABE the advisor must have a certificate in either Category A (on circular agriculture) or Category E (on sustainable entrepreneurship). There is no specific certification for the short food supply chain, however, E4 ‘sustainable earning capacity’ does include the short food supply chain.” (Netherlands country context Q&A). The advisors have to go through a specific process to get their certification in the Business Advisory System (BAS). Objective criteria based on how they are judged: 5 years of working experience of which at least 3 years should be spent as an advisor and not to be an advisor of an agricultural product selling company. As the last step, the advisors have to participate in a conversation with the BAS committee - in which the advisors can be tested if they can provide strategic advice to the farmers. This practice could be taken into consideration by testing the non-objective skills of the SFSC advisor.

In Romania currently, there is no recognition or certification but there are plans to establish a Master’s Degree Program for Agricultural Consultancy which will provide knowledge on agricultural and rural development-related consultancy for farmers. This is also not directly SFSC advice, but close to it, and with a planned online platform will contain a database of selected counselling service providers, information on the composition of AKIS partners, and NSP interventions.

In the case of Hungary, the advisory system contains dedicated SFSC-related requirements for advisors. The advisory system is managed by the Hungarian Chamber of Agriculture with a criteria system for individuals and organizations. This is regulated in a decree that contains topics and subtopics, under the topic of rural development there is a subtopic short food supply chain, for which there are no specific certificates, but for the topic of rural development, there are knowledge levels and fields that are required. Regarding knowledge and information transfer the system is quite similar to the ones in other countries, several civil organizations, non-profit organizations, and initiatives provide it for SFSC stakeholders. In addition, there is a specific short food supply chain adult training for SFSC organizers in Hungary conducted by KIS.

5.3 Minimum criteria for informal and formal advisors in D1.1. to map advisors in the EU

Hetman (2023) divided the SFSC advisors intending to identify two categories: formal and informal, each with a minimum criterion. As the collected minimum criteria are used as a starting point we present their results without any modifications.

Formal SFSC advisors: key characteristics

The role of a formal SFSC advisor includes tasks (all or just some) that involve providing advice about any aspect of the short food supply chain (primary production, processing storage, trading, distributing, and consumption) to a client. Even if the term “short food supply chain” is not directly used to describe their role, they may still be considered an SFSC advisor if their advice corresponds to our definition of SFSC (see definition above). A formal advisor may be engaged either as an employee or freelance by a public authority, a research or education institution, a private sector company (including a farm), a farmer-based organization, a non-governmental organization, or similar (Knierim et al., 2020, p. 10-11). The SFSC advisor may provide agronomical, technical, economic, legal, environmental, business, digitalization technological, or other advice.

Summary of key characteristics for formal SFSC advisors:

- Individual person (not an organization or company)
- Employed or freelance

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- Engaged by a public authority, research/education institution, private sector company, farmer-based organization, non-governmental organization, or similar
- One or more tasks in their role explicitly include providing guidance on topics relevant to the definition SFSCs, even if the term ``SFSC`` is not directly used
- Provides agronomical, technical, economic, legal, environmental, business, digitalization, technological, or similar advice
- May or may not be certified or recognized by official AKIS or national/regional advisory service body in some way as providing advisory support within SFSCs (given the lack of SFSC advisor certification in many or most EU countries)

Informal SFSC advisors' key characteristics:

The EU4Advice Grant Proposal (2022) states that typical definition and profile of the advisor, that varies according to the countries, shall be reviewed and extended in the project, considering CAP requirements, in order to include a broader scope of skills and knowledge that effectively address the current challenges faced by farmers and food producers. It can be also stated that in many cases local experts, market organizers, and non-governmental organizations provide information or informal training for SFSC actors to boost their access to the market and support their positions. Therefore, it is important to include those who provide informal advisory services in the scope of our mapping.

Informal SFSC advisors, in contrast to formal advisors, are not officially recognised as SFSC advice providers and usually do not define themselves professionally as an advisor of any kind, but nevertheless provide a form of support and guidance within SFSCs through other activities. In order to better identify an individual who could fall into this category, we draw on the concept of innovation support services (ISS), which encompass "a broader range of activities and roles such as facilitation, networking and intermediation" (Knierim et al., 2020, page 6).

In general, those activities are often "an immaterial and intangible service that involves one or several providers and one or several beneficiaries in activities in which they interact to address a more or less explicit demand emerging from a problematic situation and formulated by the beneficiaries and to co-produce the services aimed at solving the problem" (Knierim et al., 2020, page 6).

Summary of key characteristics for informal SFSC advisors:

- An individual person (not an organization or company)
- Does not define their profession or tasks within their profession in terms of providing formal advice to clients on issues that fall within the definition of SFSCs and are not explicitly reimbursed for the advisory services they provide.
- Is not certified or recognized by official AKIS or national/regional advisory service bodies
- Nevertheless, can be considered as providing a form of support and guidance within SFSCs, especially in contexts where there are no or few formal SFSC advisors, by engaging in one or more of the following activities, even if the term `SFSC` is not explicitly used:
 - creating awareness and facilitating the exchange of knowledge on SFSCs
 - providing informal consulting on SFSCs (e.g., not part of their regular job or task description, but something that comes up in the course of business or other activities)
 - demanding articulation of SFSCs for various purposes
 - networking within SFSCs or for them
 - facilitating exchanges and networks on SFSCs
 - brokering to align SFSC services
 - capacity building via training or other support within SFSCs
 - enhancing access to resources within the SFSCs

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- providing institutional support for niche innovation such as supporting with advice on laws and procedures, etc.

5.4 Analysis of the Questionnaire

Based on Figure 2 which covers the related, potential criteria areas the questions were designed to see the importance of those. At first, the respondents were required to evaluate the importance of the field of knowledge/education that the SFSC advisors would need in their work.

5.4.1 Field of knowledge

Figure 4: Field of necessary knowledge for SFSC advice Source: own edition

Based on the additional comments of the participants it can be highlighted that at a personal level what is really important is the technical knowledge, and at the community level, business-related knowledge is more important. The most relevant 3 fields are “knowledge of coordination of people and resources”, “Knowledge of legislation related to cooperation in SFSC” and “Knowledge of small-scale farming and food processing”. The technical knowledge fields such as logistics, process control, and agricultural technologies are less important for SFSC advisors.

5.4.2 Field and level of education

In the criteria system the field of education can be an easily checked requirement. Based on the answers provided by the experts, what is essential is a minimum BA/BSC level degree, but more highlighted that after a basic formal education special focused training and field experiences are more required than the formal educational certifications. Regarding the field of business and agriculture, basic education are essential and advisors might acquire any other type of certification which can be useful for their daily work.

Figure 5: Outcomes of the question: Which level of education is required for SFSC advisors? Source: own edition

5.4.3 Specific training in the countries

With this Questionnaire the list of SFSC related training, and education could not be covered but during the evaluation Focus Groups it was highlighted that such a list would be useful and could be conducted in the framework of the EU4ADVICE or COREnet project. It has been identified that in the Czech Republic, Ireland, Romania, Austria and Hungary there are specific SFSC advisor/manager trainings.

5.4.4 Previous required experience

We asked partners to say what kind of practical experience is necessary for SFSC advisors. Several replies highlighted that in general, the short-chain approach is necessary. It means that technicians should be able to supervise 'short-chain' agricultural production processes: from planning to bringing products to market, managing operational planning, agricultural production, processing of agricultural products into food, quality monitoring and preparation of products for sale and dispatch.

It is further mentioned that all SFSC groups and rural, urban territories are different, hence it is important to match those advisors who can reply to the local needs and questions and they must be able to work directly with farmers, producers. Networking, setting up activities, and business experience are also useful for them. We consider any previous practical experience that allows the adviser to be aware of the importance of SFSC neither as a consumer, as an activist/professional or as a producer. Advisors must have practical experience in how to deal with local producers, buy and consume local products. Also, experience in organization and management is crucial. Many pointed out that advisors must be familiar with the territory, which allows them to be aware of its opportunities, stakeholders, characteristics and value. The knowledge of legislation especially for small businesses, processors and short sales might be crucial but this is a special topic which is not generally available in rural areas.

5.4.5 Target group

Based on our figure 6 the fourth determining criteria field is the target group of the SFSC advice. The replying partners agreed that we should focus on the smallest actors of the food supply chains because they are those actors who face barriers to accessing knowledge for their daily businesses and there is a serious lack of information on their questions due to their diverse, innovative activities. It is important to say that SFSC advice must consider those knowledge fields which are not mainstream and mainstream advice cannot provide solutions. Apart from the farmers, SFSC advice's target groups could be SFSC market organisers, municipalities, administrations, final consumers, community kitchen managers (schools, hospitals, etc.), restaurants, neighbourhood stores, tourism operators, producer consortia, and food hubs.

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According to the COREnet Austrian expert, the key target groups are (a) SFSC initiators and (b) SFSC organisers. The function or role is key. Whether they are farmers, consumers or local government is less important. Stakeholders or participants of SFSCs are not the main target groups. This approach can be applied in later stages because it can more precisely focus on the real SFSC stakeholders.

Figure 6: Outcomes of the question: Who are the main target groups of SFSC advice? Source: own edition

5.4.6 Competences

The next question was to evaluate the importance of the competencies that the SFSC advisor needs in his or her work. The problem-solving, decision-making, the ability to improve the skills of SFSC actors, and the ability to analyse the internal environment are the most important competencies during the daily work of SFSC knowledge providers. The less important competencies are webpage editions, and technical support which can be easily received from the market. Advisors must be able to live and work together with groups of SFSC, support them to improve their businesses, and where necessary, make decisions and solve problems instead of farmers. Furthermore, knowledge of the agricultural sector, regulatory requirements, public policies and economies of scale are essential. A fundamental prerequisite is the ability to be pedagogical and sociable with actors.

Figure 7 Outcomes of the question: Necessary competencies for SFSC advisors, Source: own edition

5.4.7 Role of the SFSC advisors

Partners were asked to decide on what the main roles of the SFSC advisors are. The knowledge exchange, facilitation to access markets, supporting farmers to create their own markets, measuring risks, and searching for loans and other resources are the key roles which appear in almost every examined country. If we examine the less chosen options, again it can be pointed out that those roles which are available in general such as marketing plan, communication platforms, and organisation of local associations are less important. So, these experts must be trained and focalised on special, territorial needs and legal aspects because giving SFSC advice is not mainstream technological knowledge transfer, but rather a trust-based community building field with special, holistic supply chain experiences.

Figure 8 Outcomes of the question: Main roles of SFSC advisors. Source: own edition

5.4.8 Way of operation

We also asked if an SFSC advisor should operate as a member of an organisation or as an individual. The answers presented that it is better if there is an organisation behind the advisor in order to:

- ensure a common strategy,
- cover a wide range of knowledge by a team,
- give them more credibility,
- well known by the SFSC actors at local level,
- ensured salary,
- improvement of knowledge of advisors,
- use synergy cooperation among the advisory services across regional borders.

Numerous emphasised that to be employed is not crucial, but it is better to work with a team to be able to cover all the questions. However independent advisors have more flexibility and can be more effective and faster than advisory groups.

As in many countries the official SFSC advisory system is not operating yet personal impressions, and practical knowledge of the outcomes rely on the expertise and practical knowledge of the repliers.

5.4.9 Exclusivity

Based on the kick-off meeting workshop results, we wanted to ask partners what they take on who should be excluded from SFSC advisors. It must be prefaced that EU4Advice does not want to exclude any advisors; however, this concern is often raised during internal communications.

Figure 9 Outcomes of the question: Who should be excluded from being an SFSC advisor? Source: own edition

I would exclude anyone who does not believe in the SFSC.
The actors that are not any part of the SFSC - they have the opposite goals and should be excluded from the SFSC advisory system.
We think we should be as inclusive as possible - if their work/expertise/interest is linked to SFSCs
All should be included, based on the satisfaction of the SFSC they have already supported
Given that any player can be an advisor. The key is to have the prerequisites and skills mentioned above to be an advisor.
Those who ultimately want to build food businesses to eventually export- I think this is a hidden agenda in the export-driven food market of Ireland, and although small-scale farmers are offered governmental supports, it is often with the ultimate idea/goal to build the business to export- I think SFSC advisors should definitely have an understanding/motivation for SFSCs as a solution to so many problems in the food system, and really strive to make the SFSC concept more viable and attractive
Social communication specialists and psychologists should be included in the advisory group of the SFSC, as they can help to understand and assess the consumer's pursuit and orientation of society, in order to design strategies in the direction of consumer demand.
few should be excluded - and they will vary from country to country
My idea is to have the SFSC advisor profile as inclusive as possible, since SFSCs can be very individual and multifaceted and I don't think certain types of advisors should be excluded per se.
The advisor shouldn't sell input material.
Anyone who does not work on SFSCs!
Excluded: anyone who cannot give ongoing advice to the SFSC project, anyone with interests contrary to the SFSC, anyone who does not have the minimum knowledge/experience
I think everyone in the food chain has knowledge about SFSC. I wouldn't exclude anyone, because it might be the industry consultant who will be good at understanding the essence of SFSC. But it requires a lot of honesty.
Single persons who do not commit on sectorial strategies or negotiated and accepted practical implementation guidelines (especially regarding regulatory aspects) should not be estimated as SFSC advisors. Besides every advise which is needed, accepted and useful is welcome from whom ever it may be provided.
I think a more interesting and important question is who decides, on what basis and in whose interest? The key has to be flexibility in adapting to local needs, opportunities and resources of a specific SFSC as opposed to the other way around - getting SFSCs to fit into some predetermined model. It is important to target SFSC initiators & organisers when it comes to providing advice as opposed to the range & diversity of actors & stakeholders involved in an SFSC....
Excluded: Those who have some private interests to be part of an advisory system, and without having some intrinsic reason for it.

Table 2 Partners' opinion on exclusivity. Source: own edition

Regarding the answers we could identify two groups:

- a) Exclusion supporter group: the conventional advisors should be out of the circle

The reason behind: fear of those advisors who work with export-focused companies; fear of the pressure of companies with strong power on policy and economy; who has better access to subsidies; does not share common values; does not have interest in local economies

- b) Inclusion supporter group: no need for strong criteria

The reason behind: fear of missing important people with relevant knowledge and skills

As this question divided the experts we decided to work on this issue with the Focus Groups.

5.4.10 Summary of the results

The answers to our Questionnaire provided a better understanding of the current situation of SFSC advice in 22 countries. It must be emphasized that in most of these countries, official SFSC advice does not operate so

the answers do not reflect on the official national systems. These results proved the expectations, concepts and practical experiences of EU4Advice and COREnet partners.

In Figure 10 a summary is provided, linked to our preliminary hypothesis which was spilt into 4 areas: **competencies, knowledge, target groups and field of advice**. The main fields are legislation, business, food hygiene at small scale, and coordination. The main requested knowledge are business, law, communication and marketing, and agriculture but the territory needs must be taken into account in each case. The main target groups are the small farmers and food producers who initiate and organise SFSC at a local level. The most essential skills and competencies are problem-solving, risk analysis, and stakeholder management.

Figure 10 Summary of results from the Questionnaire based on the predefined 4 factors of SFSC advice Source: own edition

5.5 Results of focus group evaluation

At the beginning of the two Focus Group Discussions a presentation was provided in the framework of the invited experts. Then the participants were asked to share their vision of the perfect short food supply chain advisor. Their answers were collected anonymously. The answers were mainly focusing on soft skills which raised some questions about the criteria system. How can these soft, non-objective skills be measured and included in the checklist or is it even important to include these kinds of criteria in the minimum requirements? More experts defined the ideal SFSC advisor as an innovation advisor or mentor who knows the territorial endowments, has the ability to work directly with farmers as a good listener, is willing to create businesses, and new opportunities, is able to solve problems and also a creative thinker. The results can be found in Annex 6.

The discussions were structured by three questions about the target groups, measurable criteria system and exclusivity. In the following subchapter, the main results are synthesised based on the most relevant outcomes of the conversations. The two round of questions were the following:

1. Who needs the SFSC advice in your opinion? How can we improve the accessibility of the smallest/SFSC actors to help them? Who has the benefit of the knowledge transfer?
2. What do we mean by the SFSC mentality that is necessary for advisors? Can we identify it as an objective criterion? Should we understand it as an objective criterion or it might be decided at the local level on a trust basis?

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3. Based on what characteristics would you exclude someone from the SFSC advisory circle?

At the first focus group, the definition of SFSC was put on the table more times from different perspectives. The experts emphasised that it is important what we mean by Short Food Supply Chains from the aspect of to whom we would like to provide support. For example, vertical farming in Poland is a form of SFSC which supplies wholesale markets with locally grown, urban products. Though in this chain there are no farmers, it is a simple short chain that needs conventional advice and it is an eligible SFSC by the Rural Development Programme. The other perspective of the definition issue is coming from the policy side because in each Member State, the support policy defines the place, the size of the eligible farms, and the criteria of the eligible advice. ***In countries where the SFSC was incorporated into the local regulatory system and the CAP Strategic Plan there are allocated budgets for SFSC programmes including advisory services, and the SFSC ecosystem can be developed.*** It is not an ideological issue, if we have SFSC mentality or not, it is a public policy issue if we have a public policy which is open to SFSC and supportive of small holding and craft systems.

The coordinators of the EU4Advice and COREnet highlighted that after the first step, which was to launch a common mapping of potential advisors, the second step was to motivate advisors to be part of a European SFSC advisory network. Hence, from this point of view, ***the ideal SFSC advisor should be ready to share their good practices online and exchange them with others at the EU level in English.*** We are working with national communities but we want to work with an international community supporting knowledge sharing across Europe, to provide Golden Cases and to understand and adapt the replicable best practices. ***The already mapped advisors are mainly informal, so the principal question is how we can invite them to our network and to the AKIS system.***

Many said that currently, the ***SFSC advising is self-determining*** as there are no clear, legal terms for this kind of knowledge transfer system, and people who are giving advice do not think that they are giving SFSC specific advice. They can be ***internal or external advisors***: internal in a group who try to improve their knowledge and business, and external in giving advice for money or paid by public services. To map these invisible helpers who work with and support the SFSC farmers and actors, ***social network analysis should be done in each MS*** which would examine the informal knowledge transfer processes.

It is also important to note that SFSC advice ***is not only peer-to-peer advice, it may as well be a team work*** to attend to the knowledge request of SFSC actors, it might be training, a webinar, a demonstration day, or a living lab. Accordingly, an SFSC advisor is not just a person, it is a system.

The roles of ***young actors*** were brought up on both occasions. For instance, 400 local development projects were carried out in France by municipalities with improving elements for local SFSCs, and municipalities often employ young adults who take the role in developing the local food system without any experience. It is crucial for the initialising organisations such as the Chamber of Agriculture, CIVAM Network, and local authorities to have long-term experience in the field to support the young generation of advisors. In Austria, it is necessary to bring youth to the field of advice which is assisted by ***trainers' training courses to enable them to give proper advice as soon as possible.*** The training tries to show them the heterogeneous practice of SFSC and make them familiar with this specific topic, afterwards the main challenge is to keep them in the field. ***80-90% of these early-stage professionals are female*** going on maternity leave, so the system must motivate them to come back after the leave. The general aim in the case of the involvement of the young generation is to provide experienced advice, and not leave them alone.

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In the second focus group, more experts agreed that we ultimately need youth as a circle of young talents to use the competencies of new generations. As a matter of fact, **universities do not provide enough information about local food systems**, and short food supply chains. Therefore, we should invite the early stage professionals and create a mentoring system as a tool for them to learn from older generations.

It was pointed out that **we build a network to share knowledge between different generations, so we would leave the opportunity open for everyone**. The Croatian external expert agreed that we should include the young generation who come from communities who support and want to be part of our initiatives. Sometimes they are not well educated but **they have time and a strong willingness to help local initiatives and become local heroes**. The best advisors, local experts, do not have enough time to work directly with farmers, to coach them, to be mentors, but the younger enthusiastic people can take this role next to their elder mentors. It is important to emphasise that the current education system does not provide knowledge on SFSC either at secondary education or at higher level. It depends on the public policy if SFSC is highlighted or not, if it is relevant, they can combine strategy, money, curricula and investment. It is an important lack in the present education system. **Consequently, we have two important tasks in the consortiums: one is to examine the already existing good practices for available training, education, and the other is the curricula**.

It was mentioned that criteria are good if we have any but they have to take into account the meaning of SFSC, the role of farmers and the internal and external advisors in the chains. Criteria **will remain an ideological decision, because the definition of SFSC is an ideological issue now**. Thus, an objective criteria system can not be defined in the current European legislative system. The COREnet Charta, which is prepared by the COREnet consortium and was discussed at the joint General Assembly, will provide a recommendation for SFSC definition which can be used for the final criteria system.

Regarding the **establishment of an objective and measurable criteria system**, more opinions were confronted. The main purpose of the original call was to promote the access of advisors to the official AKIS so the criteria system must reinforce their access to the future network which must be adaptable to the national AKISs. To reach this objective one **important step is to examine the Rural Development Programmes (RDP) between 2014 and 2022**. We can emerge from the place of knowledge transfer in SFSC if in RDP participation of the advisor is obligatory for tenders. In a 3 or 5 year period, they can learn to work together and the quality of advice can give high value. **These experiences might be defined as criteria systems which might be adapted by the MSs according to their own systems and needs**. Another approach said that **objectifying the SFSC advice is not an issue at this moment when mainly informal advisory methods work at the field level, therefore improving soft skills and adapting them at the local level is more important as a first intervention**. SFSC advisors have a more specific profile than other conventional technology advisors, that can be validated by SFSC actors. This on-field validation and substantive replicability is more important than establishing an objective criteria list for official AKIS.

Concerning exclusivity, everybody agreed that saying in or out in the SFSC network/advisory system is a misleading direction. The issue of exclusivity can be observed from different perspectives, firstly, from the target group. In the term AKIS the "S" means System, so **in the case of the primary target group, we would focus on those integrated into a system, such as an NGO or in a locally/nationally/EU-level funded project consortium that is engaged with SFSC**. From this approach, the individuals who belong to any non-profit communities might be part of the AKIS (whether farmers, local authorities, individual mentors or consumers). Who are not integrated into any systems we would keep them outside, but defining certain categories such as people interested without any practical knowledge, or real involvement in SFSC so far.. However, we have to be aware that there are countries where these kinds of systems do not exist, like in Romania. **Secondly,**

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the exclusivity can start from the operation of the SFSC Advisory Network. It means that **in the first phase, we should invite everybody and we should be as open as we can without any strict criteria system.** The UK, NL and IR experts highlighted that those who work with big agricultural companies have a lot of experience, wide networks, and knowledge of farmers. These companies are actors of the chains and the question is what is their ultimate goal in providing advice. Big company advisors in Ireland, try to build up small companies to be able to produce for export, they have a lot of experience and it is not a problem when a conventional advisor would like to provide knowledge for small companies. (NOTE: It is a highly debated topic because FR, PL, AT, RO, HU experts are definitely against the integration of conventional big industry advisors.) **In the second phase, we should measure the engagement and involvement of the advisors and create a kind of “blacklist” for those who are misusing the SFSC advisory network.** To ensure the engagement of new actors to SFSC the consortium should design a “process of growth” to let in those who want to do something, be part of the ecosystem and analyse how they can contribute to developing the common chain of trust. *But these criteria can be decided at national level, as an overall framework that fits for every country can not be established due to the diversity and different approaches.* New technological tools such as rating systems, network visualisation technologies and AI might support this process.

This kind of inclusivity helps us to invite and embed the already working advisory methods and different kinds of knowledge from the value chains. However, it must be pointed out that without those soft skills and competencies which were listed in the Questionnaire, the advisors won't be able to work with SFSC actors as it is a special field of advice where soft skills can be crucial.

This inclusivity also means that SFSC advice is not just peer-to-peer advice, all types of knowledge transfer can be combined, moreover, the co-production of knowledge is also a way of providing advice. Co-production of research and knowledge with all the stakeholders in the system is relevant because it is not a well-established process yet. There can be so much lack of knowledge and competencies in the system that can be completed by intermediaries, researchers, innovation brokers, technology providers and so on.

Figure 11 Growth process model. Source: own edition based on the Focus Group Discussions Source: own edition

6 Conclusions

It can be concluded that based on the outcomes of our research a **strict minimum checklist of core requirements cannot be established.**

The results showed that the **SFSC Knowledge Transfer Ecosystem** should be based on all SFSC actors who are engaged in local development, suitable roles in knowledge transfer for SFSC initiators, SFSC knowledge providers and knowledge co-creators, and finally, based on a supportive environment that is able to define SFSC and the place of small farmers.

The SFSC Knowledge Transfer Ecosystem is visualised on Figure 12. The figure summarises whose contribution could be integrated into the SFSC Knowledge Transfer Network created by COREnet and EU4Advice consortiums (with contribution from sister projects such as EUFARMBOOK, i2connect, etc.). Three main groups can be identified: **SFSC organisers, SFSC knowledge providers and SFSC knowledge co-creators.** The SFSC Knowledge Transfer Network is based on these actors and an enabling environment is necessary for the appropriate operation, functioning of the network.

Figure 12 SFSC Knowledge Transfer Ecosystem based on the results of the Questionnaire and Focus Group Discussions Source: own edition

The **main output of the deliverable** is synthesised in Table 3 where the recommended topics for selection of SFSC advisors are collected which can be used by the MSs for the integration process. The first column presents the main recommended measurable and objective topics for setting-up the selection criteria. These

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are the **field and level of education, the target groups, competencies, skills, organisational background, way of advice and references.**

Finally, we observed the integrability of these factors to the AKIS system coming from the available information. Unfortunately, there is currently little information available on the Member States' AKISs and the specific rules governing the SFSC advisory system, but this will be necessary for further studies.

If we consider Figure 3 as a step-by-step approach to strengthen systematic innovation capacity, by competences, capacities, and capabilities, it can be transferred to the SFSC consultancy methodology. Therefore, mentioned skills should be considered as minimum core criteria to enter the SFSC advisory system as without these skills the advisor is not capable of giving proper advice on the field of SFSCs.

In summary, in terms of integrability, it is assumed that many factors are already in line with the current AKISs. **Those characteristics which are specific in the case of SFSC, like target groups and skills, should be considered during the further steps.**

For the establishment of a recommended list of requirements, we believe that it is important to show **how many different designations/names/roles can be linked to SFSC advisors** (see Table 2), and which actors could be also identified as advisors. The list basically reflects the outcomes of the Questionnaire and the Focus Group Discussions done in our Research.

Advisors' denomination	Description of the tasks and activities
Advisor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gives advice to farmers to solve and identify problem, challenges, production, management constraint, etc
Facilitator/mentor/coach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aims at the development of shared meaning, language and objectives between dialogue partners in order to stimulate change and develop innovative solutions • Generates innovation (policy or technological) • Supports problem-solving
Farmers' market organiser	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports organization development and capacity building by fostering knowledge, skills and abilities • Empowers farmers to investigate new options to increase the viability of their farm businesses
Basket community manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports farmers, producers with developing their products, • Creates common platform for selling, marketing, creating good quality pictures
Tourism agent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide visibility for farmers, producers. • Inclusion to local tourism activities
Consultant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advisory communication to enhance problem solving ability
Marketing specialist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports the development or establishment of marketing strategies and tools tailor-made for the community
Mediator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conflict management

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Communication specialist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitates communication and knowledge sharing, and awareness creation among partners
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Table 3 Type of informal SFSC advisors, Based on Kneirim et al, (2020), Koutsuris (2018), Leeuwis (2004), Klerkx and Leeuwis (2008), Hoffmann et al. (2009) with additional aspects based on the outcomes of the research

It was confirmed by the outcomes of the Focus Group Discussions, as the experts highlighted to be as inclusive as possible since the key requirements are basic knowledge, commitment, and trust which can be learned in most of the cases or could be covered by a team. This is followed by the development of different capacities for which it is crucial to have an enabling, supporting environment where the work of the advisor is recognized, acknowledged, paid, and included in the knowledge transfer system.

It is agreed that the advisor should have the right tools and enough time to fulfil the needs of SFSC actors for which appropriate supporting regulations and an institutional system are required. In addition demand and appropriate customer needs are crucial also. All in all, these are the basic recommended requirements for now which are linked to Figure 1. Qualification of an advisor (Kneirim et al., 2020) means that we require the “Basic disposition + attitude” and all the other aspects might be developed by the personal path of the SFSC advisor.

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Table 4 Criteria system of SFSC advisors

Topics	Recommended subtopics	Recommendations for Integration to AKIS
Education level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Practical experience ● Bachelor degree (depends on national rules) ● Special focused training and practical experience ● Vocational training ● Other 	<p>The currently available CAP Strategic Plans do not provide instructions for the required education field for SFSC advisors.</p> <p>WP3 can provide recommendations for minimum requirements and special training</p>
Education field	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agriculture ● Innovation brokerage ● Business ● Administration ● Social studies ● Food engineering ● Communication & marketing ● Nutrition ● Community building ● Impact data measurement ● Platform & IT ● Multi-media communication ● Logistics ● Rural development ● Social revitalization ● Teamwork and participation ● Green public purchase ● Associationism ● Other 	<p>The current CAP Strategic Plans do not provide instructions for the required education level for formal SFSC advisors however some MS determine the minimum education level and the scope of education.</p> <p>WP3 can provide recommendations for minimum requirements and special training</p>

<p>Target groups of the advisory activity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Small producers (less than 10 ha) ● Small-scale food processing ● Informal group of farmers ● Basket scheme communities ● Organic farmers ● Other SFSC facilitators ● Local Action Groups (LAG) ● Tourism operators ● Producer consortia; food hubs ● Education Institutes, Catering Companies, HoReCa, Retail ● Administrations, final consumers, community ● Kitchen managers (school, hospital, etc), ● Restaurants, neighbourhood stores ● CSA farms ● Social cooperatives ● Municipalities ● Other 	<p>As current SFSC stakeholders are often not eligible for EU funds, the NGOs, formal farmers' communities might be the collection point of those who can benefit from SFSC advice.</p>
<p>Field of advice (SFSC advisors must have relevant experience at least on one of the listed scopes)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Food legislation, ● Food processing technology ● Marketing and distribution ● Taxation and legal questions ● Organic, regenerative farming, ● Cooperation, food-coops ● Logistics ● Packaging ● Rural development ● CAP tenders 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Administration process for CAP ● Social economy ● Other 	
Competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strategic thinking ● Creativity ● Problem- solving ● Active listening ● Motivation ● Understanding of the context ● Fostering teamwork ● Being easily understood ● Resilience and adoption of the millennium goals or the 2030 agenda ● Community building, creating a regional trusted collaborative network, systemic system change management and tools, shaping collaboration between citizens and farmers ● Financial sustainability of SFSC ● Effective collaboration; application of regulations on tax & food safety; organisational model. ● Official advice is focussed on accessing funding ● Other 	The basic competencies which were selected by partners are part of the classical advisory service which ensures the adaptability of SFSC advisors. They can be completed at the further stages of the project.

Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To exchange knowledge ● To diversify local cooperation ● To show, demonstrate, and explain the farmers how they can access the market ● To connect with all actors in the chain ● To have an insight of the governmental and other special (loan, business angel etc.) support system helping in the community ● To provide up-to-date knowledge of local opportunities ● To facilitate the access to market of small farmers ● project management and set up businesses courses and training programs. ● Further, experience in funding tools for SFSC and how to navigate and manage application steps. ● Understanding the farmers and having the experience of working with farmers. ● Other 	<p>The listed skills make the SFSC advisors distinguishable from conventional advice because those skills are crucial which makes advisors capable of supporting SFSC organisations. Without these skills, advisors won't be able to understand the SFSC ecosystem.</p> <p>These soft skills are measurable with difficulty, they might be evaluated by local results.</p>
References	<p>Advisor</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● has already participated in setting-up SFSC group ● has already taken part of EU or national SFSC related project ● has organised farmers' market, direct selling events, open farm days, ● has operated box schemes, CSA ● has provided P2P learning for SFSC actors 	<p>The potential value of a contact with an unknown advisory person is mainly described by the projects and experience a person has. This is demonstrated by practical examples related to the work of the advisory person. Practically it could be underlined by links to those projects where the person was involved in.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● supporting creation of local chains, cooperatives, farmers' shops ● has supported establishment of public procurement <p>And any kind of references from which the advisor gained experience in SFSC fields.</p>	
Organisational background	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Organisation ● Individual 	<p>If advisors have an organisational background the common strategies and actions can be evaluated together towards an overall goal or objective.</p> <p>However the mapped advisors are mainly informal and their current status cannot ensure the organisational background.</p> <p>It is recommended to examine how this background can be offered to potential advisors.</p>
Way of giving advice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Peer-to-peer ● Learning organisation ● Community of practice ● Online webinars ● Other 	<p>All types of advice are already integrated into AKIS.</p>

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Weblinks

<https://www.ruralfacilitator.eu/en/> Project reference number: 2019-1-CZ01-KA202-061270

<https://i2connect-h2020.eu/>

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8 Annexes

1. Annex 1 - Results of the kick-off meeting workshop

EU4Advice Workshop – Who are the advisors and who is not or should be out of the system?

In the groups during the kick-off meeting the main issue was how the experts could define the SFSC advisors and how they could exclude those advisors who cannot be identified in the field of SFSC. How is it possible to distinguish the SFSC advisory services from other agricultural extension services? How will an SFSC advisor operate in the fields? The main objective of these discussions was to map the experts' different approaches and to observe the expected and required experience which may exclude the not-ready-to-be SFSC advisors.

1st round: The main questions discussed by the experts during the first round were:

What are the main criteria for being an SFSC advisor? Where does the work of an SFSC advisor start?

- It is hard to define the exact SFSC advisors' job, as the right skills depend on the topics and products. It means that mainly all the product type requires different type of skills such as milk production, poultry meat processing, traditional fish products, etc.
- There are many network organizations in Europe that are able to manage the network and application of SFSC advisor. The main task is to find those networks that have competencies and an understanding of SFSC. We should list those network organisations who could be our partners during the implementation of the project.
- There are many informal facilitators and farmers' market organisers who can be defined as SFSC advisors because they are able to talk to more people.
- Innovation brokers, facilitators, and market organisers are still in this field, we should target them with special training, organisations, and platforms.
- One of the most debated issues was where the short chain starts and at which point the advisors shall come into action. Most of the participants agreed that the task of the advisor starts from the ready-to-use/ready-to-sell products and not from the primary production. One said it depends on the chains because a CSA action can start at the primary production as the farmers must learn how to plan a year in a greenhouse. It was a small sticking point because some of them agreed that for these questions we have a well-organized advisory-, in some countries AKIS system and the main issue is how they can arrange the CSA's processes and the plant protection, nutrient management etc. topics are not relevant from our point of view. Others thought that we shouldn't split the topics of production and sales on this small scale, because it is not cost- and time-effective.
- The question was raised if the national NCPs have an up-to-date list of the includable organisations (NGOs, research institutes, market organisers, platform managers, extension service providers?)
- Since there is no targeted advisory and training service currently and we should train the future advisors, it is suggestible to involve the new generation, students and train them in these specific fields.
- The final remark in this round was that we should identify business support networks: it means that SFSC advisory service must focus on the best/good business models, that is why we should list the already working business support network who could work in SFSC.

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2nd round: In the second round the experts raised the question of how we can define the SFSC advisory services and criteria, which organization must be involved in the different countries. How should the process of SFSC system building be launched?

- The first idea was to elaborate a rating system to measure advisory service. An example can be the Google, Trip Advisor etc. rating methods where we have feedback about the first trials from the field/practice. It can be managed by the Living Labs.
- We shall develop a proper onboarding process which will be based on, on the one hand, the current experience, and on the other hand the student from the uni:
 - the first step of the process is to identify what kind of experts they have now;
 - second step is to take into consideration that it is a process with different steps;
 - the development of the process is supported by industrial guides to begin
 - Beyond the ready-to-use guide from the industrial sectors we should map the relations to other projects and make an inventory;
 - for operating the process, we need network, practical, strategic knowledge.
- One of the main criteria of the SFSC advisory system is to be transparent: who, where, and why. The advisors must be transparent and the operation level as well because it helps in trust building. The currently working SFSC advisors' work is also based on trust.
- The first step to define criteria is to define the profile of the advisor.
- Almost everybody agreed that a public server also can be an advisor e.g.: from local governments or food safety authorities. We have several best practices from the partner countries which can help us to see how this group can be involved.
- We should specify what we want to expect from advisors and list the necessary knowledge fields and sectors.
- In each case we need multidisciplinary knowledge from the advisors thus we have to train them.

3rd round: In this group, the main topic of the discussion expanded the minimum expected experience from SFSC advisors.

- One hot point was whether the companies' advisors could be SFSC advisors. From the Campden Bri point of view and experience, their food safety and quality management advisors are also from a company that can be called SFSC advisors if we train them for these specialties. Some participants said that SFSC advisors must be independent and this approach must follow the SCAR AKIS's recommendations. Inge van Oost had a presentation which appointed the AKIS advisors must be independent.
- The question of who is in and who is out depends on the skills and experience in SFSC fields. All the SFSC advisors must have at least 2-3 years of experience in any topic of SFSC. The practical skills can be gained in either agriculture or food industry or any related topic. Later somebody added business, webshop management, farmers' market or CSA management, marketing, communication, logistics, and environmental experiences.
- It suddenly means that most of the participants agreed that fresh people from the universities cannot be SFSC advisors however we could work on special training and mentoring system for them. It would provide a clear way for these young people and a common understanding of SFSC.

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- It is a common experience from the different countries that more NGOs work with SFSC groups. They help them, and trust them for a long time, which can serve also basis for the new networks, and platforms. The consortium shall map these NGOs and involve them in the partnership.
- The CSAs' actions also created many platforms, and experiences which are different in the member countries. We should have a special focus on their needs and the possibilities for knowledge transfer that they can provide for this project.
- The farmers-to-farmers knowledge transfer can be also a crucial point for us such as field visits, experimental farmings, cross visits, and NEFERTITI project created guidelines for these actions that we could use. We should organize farmers-to-farmers events and observe how we could manage these events in the frame of our system.
- Academic research is not an SFSC topic, we should be aware of that but it can be implemented, and can supply what you are doing.

2. Annex 2 – Rural Facilitator competence catalogue conclusions

Conclusions

Based on qualitative and quantitative data, the analysis unveiled key common shared opinions and differences between the nations. The desk research, questionnaires both long and short, and the interviews were all aimed at compiling the traits of the desired facilitator role. The samples had a wide variety of people coming from different professional and academic backgrounds.

Each nation had its own hierarchy of the listed skills, competencies and knowledge; however, the commonalities weigh much more than the given differences. The differences can be seen at the end of the questionnaire's analysis, and at the national comparison parts. Each country should consider the specific desires of its own questionnaires, but there were mostly subtle differences when it came to the most important areas of the desired facilitator role. The short questionnaire had a mixture of skills, competencies and knowledge, while the long one asked about these separately. If we want to draw conclusions on the possible areas, it is best if we try to organize them into groups, which can foreshadow possible modules.

Leadership skills

Being a leader and being able to lead others requires a certain set of skills. Numerous interpersonal skills were given high importance in the samples. Leaders help themselves and others to be as effective as possible. They can set directions and manage people below them. The facilitator should be able to articulate the needs of the small-scale farmers, help them and negotiate with them as well as the stakeholders, and should also be able to use his/her management skills when dealing with customers.

The facilitator can serve as some sort of a coach, who can motivate and inspire actors in the rural area to achieve a common vision. Interpersonal skills are a big part of the leader's toolkit, as they are continuously engaged with people.

Network building is also a valued trait of the leaders, as it can expand the farmers' possibilities to areas that have been uncharted for them. If the facilitator manages to establish trust between him/her and the farmers, a new chapter of collaborative efforts can bring several advantages to the rural area.

Knowledge of SFSCs

In order for the facilitators to be an effective asset for the short food supply chains, they must possess prior knowledge of the operation of SFSCs. A lot of knowledge can belong under this topic, along with the national differences connected to each nation's specific situation. From food processing through knowledge of the

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internal/external environment of the SFSCs to legislation, this knowledge prepares the facilitator to deal with any upcoming task related to SFSCs. Tools and techniques, and inside knowledge on the processes related to SFSCs will enable the facilitator to understand each aspect of running an SFSC from the inside out, making him/her a valuable asset in rural communities.

Business knowledge

It is not enough for the facilitator to be up-to-date on rural development and SFSCs, in order to be an effective market entity, he/she also has to have business-related knowledge. Using new sales techniques or mixed market elements can be a source of extra knowledge on things that the farmers might not be as informed on. Adding the facilitators' business proficiency to the farmers' available knowledge can boost their effectiveness and chances of being a successful actor on the market. The facilitator can assist in market sales as well as many other important areas related to selling the farmers' products.

Food hygiene

Food hygiene has received eminent importance in every nation's sample. Such knowledge is indispensable for the facilitator to see through several processes regarding SFSCs, and in order for him/her to be able to recognize flaws within the chains, and to be able to effectively deal with them.

Communication

Communication makes up a part of the previously mentioned leadership skills, however, more attention could be focused on the topic. Being able to compromise and manage conflicts, and coming up with win-win solutions is as much of a question of communication as of leadership itself. If the facilitator can find a common language between stakeholders and farmers, it can minimise the amount of possible conflict and can help both parties advance towards a fruitful cooperation. Internal communication within the chains and external communication are both vital for the success of the SFSCs.

Marketing knowledge

Even if marketing is a part for business skills, increased focus should be administered on this topic. Marketing is a topic complex enough to be represented in a separate module. Both traditional and online marketing elements could prove beneficial for the SFSCs. The facilitators added extra knowledge on such topics could provide insight into areas which the farmers might not be as familiar with.

These possible modules are based both on the separate and combined findings of IO1, the members of the consortium should consider how they see the modules benefit at their own national level, as well as in a comprehensive way.

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3. Annex 3 Questionnaire on the minimum requirements of SFSC advisors

EU4ADVICE Questionnaire - WP2 Task 2.1

Questionnaire on the minimum requirements of SFSC advisors

WP2 - Task 2.1

Set-up minimum requirements and criteria for inclusion (M1-M12). Task leader: KIS

Other task partners: COPA, UGENT, UHOH, UCD

Each project partner is asked to fill this out to the best of their ability **by 14 August 2023**.

Overview of the questionnaire and the aims

The present questionnaire has been prepared for Task 2.1 in order to find the minimum requirements the EU4Advice Project will suggest for an official Short Food Supply Chain advisor that might even be supported by the AKIS system, counselling based on the current situation in each partner country. During the filling of the questionnaire please focus on the current situation in the country you are referring to.

The aim of this task is to define those minimum skills, competencies, knowledge areas that an SFSC advisor should have! In this task we will prepare a checklist, a competence matrix for the selection criteria for SFSC advisors to be part of the EU network, and of prerequisites for advisory services to be integrated into national AKIS and comply with national CAP Strategic Plans, in order to include a wide diversity of advisor profiles. This will be validated by the SWG SCAR-AKIS and SWG Food Systems.

We know that in most of the countries there is no such a definition of short food supply chain advisors, but our aim now is to find those minimum criterias that are important to be required from someone who wants to give proper advise! If you don't have a SFSC advisory system in your country yet then please try to answer the questions based on what SFSC actors (for example farmers, producers, local governments, HoReCa sector actors, etc.) would need in terms of knowledge. Find someone who have insights on what knowledge gaps are present at local level.

In the end we are looking for those actors who can fill in these knowledge gaps - they are the SFSC advisors!

Who could be identified as a short food supply chain advisor?

In order to support you while you are filling out the questionnaire we would like to let you know that there is not a settled definition of short food supply chain advisor. This is one of the steps for us to set-up the minimum criteria for them.

Then how can you identify someone as an SFSC advisor?

Think of people who organize farmers' markets, manage CSA farms, organize basket communities, work together with groups of small-scale producers, create a platform for small-scale producers where they can sell their products - for example an online platform,

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or a direct sale channel towards hotels, restaurants, catering, public catering, etc. What kind of skill and competences, knowledge they should have?

Who could be interviewed or asked to fill the questionnaire?

Please try to find those actors in your country who cope with small-scale producers, who has insights on this topic - this could be someone from the field, like an advisor who has been identified as a non-formal SFSC advisor previously (in the mapping task of the project), someone who organize farmers' markets, manage basket communities, Community Supported Agriculture (CSA) schemes, etc.

If any of the provided information is not enough, please reach out to us:
kujani.katalin@kisleptek.hu and nagy.viktoria@kisleptek.hu

For better understanding the team of KISLÉPTÉK prepared a figure about the complexity of the relevant fields and attributions of SFSC advisory activities which determine the framework of the SFSC specific advice. This figure defines those 4 aspects of the expected requirements which demonstrate the minimum criteria for the SFSC advisors to be able to provide appropriate knowledge:

- field of advice;
- education field and level of the advisor;
- target groups of the advisory activity;
- competencies and skills of the advisors.

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Please check this figure as a basis for the analysis of the situation in your country:

The possible areas of minimum requirements for Short Food Supply Chain advisors

Partner organization filling out this form *

Saját válasz

Name of contact person *

Saját válasz

E-mail address *

Saját válasz

Which country are you referring to while you are filling the questionnaire? *

Saját válasz

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Please evaluate the importance of the following knowledge that the SFSC advisors would need in their work. *

	1	2	3	4	5	I don't know
Logistic knowledge	<input type="radio"/>					
Technical knowledge in the field	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge on process control	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge of food hygiene	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge on small scale farming and food processing	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge of tourism	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge of business plan preparation	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge of the technological solutions in the production	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge on performance management	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge of leadership techniques	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge of negotiation techniques	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge of	<input type="radio"/>					

Knowledge of motivation techniques						
Knowledge of coordination of people and resources	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge of techniques and tools of short chain organisation SFSCs	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge of agricultural process control	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge of legislation related to cooperation in SFSC	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge of rural development programs and other supports	<input type="radio"/>					
Knowledge of technological innovation	<input type="radio"/>					

Which field of education is necessary for an SFSC advisor to be able to answer the questions from SFSC actors? Multiply choice is possible. *

- Agriculture
- Horticulture
- Innovation brokerage
- Business
- Administration
- Social studies
- Food engineering
- Egyéb:

Please list if any other field is missing in your opinion:

Saját válasz

Which level of education is required for an SFSC advisor to be able to answer the * questions of an SFSC actors?

- Secondary technical and vocational school
- vocational education (for adults)
- University BA/Bsc degree
- University MA/Msc degree
- Phd
- post-doctor
- specific training
- any other (please indicate if there is any special education level required in your country)
- Egyéb:

Is there any specific training in your country for short food supply chain advisors? *

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

What kind of previous practical experience (eg.: food processing at small-scale * or higher scale, purchasing method, producing, set-up businesses, innovation brokerage, project management, any special advisory services, etc.) in SFSC do you think would be necessary to be requested from SFSC advisors? Or do you see any practice in your country?

Saját válasz

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Who could be the target audience of SFSC advisory activities in your country? *
Please tick all the relevant ones.

Please check the figure above and if you have any other specific target groups please list it also!

- agriculture primary producer less than 10 ha
- primary producer >10ha
- small-scale food processing
- middle-size food processing
- informal group of farmers
- farmers organization
- basket scheme
- CSA farmers
- cooperatives
- social cooperatives
- municipalities
- organic farmers
- technology providers
- innovation brokers
- other SFSC facilitators
- students
- Local Action Groups (LAG)
- I don't know
- other:

Any other target groups?

Saját válasz

Please evaluate the importance of the following competences that the SFSC advisor needs in his or her work. *

On the scale below, mark the value from 1 to 5 that you consider appropriate. The value of 1 is the least important, the value of 5 is the most important.

	1	2	3	4	5	I don't know
Strategic thinking	<input type="radio"/>					
Analytical thinking	<input type="radio"/>					
Creativity	<input type="radio"/>					
Problem solving	<input type="radio"/>					
Active listening	<input type="radio"/>					
Coordination	<input type="radio"/>					
Motivation	<input type="radio"/>					
Objectivity	<input type="radio"/>					
Flexibility	<input type="radio"/>					
Leadership	<input type="radio"/>					
Patience and endurance	<input type="radio"/>					
Sensitivity to situation	<input type="radio"/>					
Understanding of the context	<input type="radio"/>					
Being easily	<input type="radio"/>					

Being easily understood	<input type="radio"/>					
Change management competency	<input type="radio"/>					
Encouraging continuous learning	<input type="radio"/>					
Fostering team work	<input type="radio"/>					
Establishing focus	<input type="radio"/>					
Forecasting	<input type="radio"/>					
Stakeholder management	<input type="radio"/>					
Using IT	<input type="radio"/>					
Mobil device application using	<input type="radio"/>					
Online marketing elements using	<input type="radio"/>					

Please evaluate the importance of the following skills that the SFSC advisor needs in his or her work. On the scale below, mark the value from 1 to 5 that you consider appropriate. The value of 1 is the least important, the value of 5 is the most important.

	1	2	3	4	5	I don't know
Ability to solve problems and achieve the goals	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to make decisions	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to set targets	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to think synthetically	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability recognize risks	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to explain and repeat explanations if necessary	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to monitor the work processes	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to forecast & predict major changes that might occur	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to evaluate accurately future directions and risks	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to						

understand existing and emerging trends in technology and business	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to analyse the external context of the SFSC	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to analyse the internal environment of the SFSC	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to improve skills of member of SFSC	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to apply new products/ services	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to use new sales techniques	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to use mixed market elements	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to use community channels	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to use digital communication	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to use basic web editing programs	<input type="radio"/>					
Ability to organize workshops	<input type="radio"/>					

Ability to lead workshops

Ability to lead workshops

What kind of previous practical experience (eg.: food processing at small-scale or higher scale, purchasing method, producing, set-up businesses, innovation brokerage, project management, any special advisory services, etc.) in SFSC do you think would be necessary to demand from SFSC advisors? Or are you aware of any practice in your country?

Saját válasz

What are the main roles of the SFSC advisor? Please tick all the relevant ones!

- To build new networks
- To exchange knowledge
- To diversify local cooperation
- To connect with all actors in the chain
- To increase the synergy between the several actors
- To organise farmers' associations
- To solve conflicts between farmers and consumers
- To look for special supports
- To generate ideas and think outside the box
- To analyse the changes of markets
- To facilitate the access to market of small farmers
- To show, demonstrate, and explain the farmers how they can access the market
- To realize the market's needs
- To prepare a strategy plan
- To prepare a common marketing plan for the local community
- To have an insight of the governmental and other special (loan, business angel etc.) support system helping in the community
- To provide up-to-date knowledge of local opportunities
- To introduce the available business tools to the community
- To teach the usage of online tools to the community
- To organize the community building events
- To watch, guide, and correct the work performed by the SFSCs
- To prepare for the possible risks
- To be able to write proposals/ tenders Legal service
- To maintain local value repository

Egyéb:

What are the questions/topics/fields which are important for SFSC actors but actually they cannot access this knowledge in the official advice channels? *

Saját válasz

**What is your opinion or what is the situation in your country:
An SFSC advisor should operate as a member of an organisation or as an individual? ***

- as a member of an organisation
- as an individual
- I don't know

Please explain your opinion on the question above!

Saját válasz

What is your opinion who should be excluded from being SFSC advisor? *

- big industrial advisor
- no-till advisor
- plant protection advisor
- input material provider
- not independent advisors
- I don't know

What is your opinion on who should be included or excluded from the SFSC advisory system? Please write any ideas you might have. *

Saját válasz

Küldés

[Ürlap tartalmának törlése](#)

Google Úrlapokon soha ne adjon meg jelszavakat.

Az űrlapot a(z) Kislépték Munkacsapat domainen belül hozták létre. [Visszaélés jelentése](#)

Google Úrlapok

D 2.1	Dissemination level PU-Public	62 / 81
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4. Annex 4 Presentation and methodology for the Focus Group Discussions

Dr. András Sebők On-line consultation 23/09/2023

Conceptual framework and the methodology focused on Task 3.1 Elaboration of guidelines for SFC- related advice

András Sebők, Kinga Varsányi, Adrienn Hegyi
Campden BRI Hungary

 Funded by the European Union

eu4advice.eu

Objectives and challenges of the WP3

- Develop innovative contents and tools to facilitate the upscaling of SFSCs to increase the viability and sustainability of European farms and food SMEs
- Elaborating co-designed guidelines and tools for SFSC related advice and training materials
- Promoting cost-effective innovations that improve the economic, environmental and social performance of the activities of SFSCs.

D 2.1	Dissemination level PU-Public	63 / 81
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Approach

- We will use the competency framework developed by EIT Food (2021)
- Take into account the conclusions of the "EU Blueprint Erasmus Fields: Agrifood Scenarios 2030" developed by Jaques Trinikenes (WUR) (2023)
 - trends: sustainable production, digitalisation, business model (SFSC is a business model)
 - 3 scenarios: Sustainable path, High-Tech path, Established path
 - Key topics for scenarios: sustainable production, digitalisation, business models, AKIS structure, impact Covid 19, Ukraine war, energy crises considered
 - Current developments push toward both sustainable and high-tech pathways
 - Lessons learned for EU4Advice: the consideration of the combination of the two pathways might be useful

Timetable

- We have to complete tasks for 2 milestones in the next 9 months:
 - M5 (T3.1) - Identification of SFSC needs in terms of advice (CBHU), SFSC needs (LL leaders) **December 2023**
 - M6 (T3.2) Draft guidelines and tools to be implemented a LL level (CBHU) **March 2024**
-
- Agree, accept the conceptual framework **14th July 2023**
 - Identify the training needs of SFSC advisors, including country-specific needs, and prepare a complete list for prioritisation **7th September 2023**
 - Review and adjustment of the design in the annual meeting **25-27th Oct 2023**
 - Report Milestone M5 **31st Dec2023**
 - Report milestone M6 **31st March 2024**

D 2.1	Dissemination level PU-Public	64 / 81
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EIT Food Education – Competency framework

Source: EIT Food

Competency levels (EIT Food)

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4 levels per Competency (EIT Food)

EXPLORE: An individual is **laying the foundations** in contributing to the sector.

They are relatively new to their field of influence

"Lay the foundation of the application" – **apply basic principles, methods**

PRACTICE: An individual is able to **turn ideas into actions** and put into practice the foundations they have already developed to the benefit of their field of influence.

"Turn ideas into action" – **analyse, appraise, collect, create, design.**

MASTER: An individual has mastered the principles of practice and is able/in a position to **deliver impact** within their field of influence and the sector.

"Deliver impact"- **develop strategies, critically analyse, create opportunities, influence**

INSPIRE: An individual is already performing at a level which **transforms the system** and has an influence that goes beyond his field and the wider sector.

"Transform the system" – **educate and support, guide, challenge others**

Training needs of the advisors

- The necessary competencies of the advisors shall be defined by considering the need for advice of the SFSC actors.
- Taking into account the needs, barriers and constraints of knowledge transfer to advisors and to SFSC members by advisors
- The training needs of the advisors shall be defined by the identification of the likely gaps in the competency of the advisors. These gaps are specific for the individual.
- The need for advice of the SFSC actors, competencies of the advisors and the likely gaps in the competency of the advisors shall be defined by the own experiences of the WP partners (including former projects), input from EU4Advice, **CoreNet**, other running projects and literature.

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Training needs of the advisors (2)

- The diverse needs for advice shall be satisfied by a team of advisors with complementary competencies at the regional (national?) level. Not all advisors shall deliver all advice.
- The specific needs for implementing training of advisors shall be defined by the people/ organisation responsible region for coordinating their activities in the region.
- We shall provide a choice, menu of available training materials

EU4Advice- WP3 Conceptual Framework (draft v5. 10.07.2023)

How to use Table 1. Training needs of SFSC advisors to satisfy the needs of SFSC actors for advice and training

Competency category as defined by the EIT Food Competency Framework	Needs of the farmers, SFSC members/actors for advice	Need for training of farmers, SFSC members/actors in addition to advice and competency level	Necessary competence/training need of the advisors to deliver advice for SFSC actors and competency level	Explanations. comments
Consider 1 of the 8 EIT Food competency categories	Describe the need with all specific details, ideas	Indicate if specific training is necessary and feasible beyond advice	Describe the need with all specific details, ideas to meet the actors' needs for advice. Add competency level.	Phase1. working material, internal use
1. Technology management	Legal requirements of food, best practice guides	Training on production environment	Legal requirements of food for production environment of cheese, best practice guides. (Explore).	Example

Process of defining the training material for developing competence of SFSC advisors

13 23/09/2023

Content of the training materials (1)

14 23/09/2023

- Consider that the advice provided to the farmers, SFSC actors should be practical and focused on the challenge. Consider the necessary level of competence of the advisors to enable this and the necessary level of competence of the users of the advice
- Even if 2-3 topics/competence category is elaborated, this will mean more than 20 training materials – there should be a satisfactory choice to satisfy diverse needs
- The training material should be concise. Explain principles, main elements of good practices. Provide practical examples, exercises.

Content of the training materials (2)

- Limit the description of the background, theoretical explanation to the minimum
- Recommend methods, tools to support the delivery
- Provide references, links to access additional information, best practice guides
- A template will be developed jointly

Delivery of advice for the farmers, SFSC actors

- Farmers, food businesses prefer bilateral, confidential advice on-site. The time for individual advice can be reduced, and efficiency can be increased by the use of "collective research and advice."
- The method is made of two phases:
 - pre-competitive, preparatory, collective phase
No need to use or disclose any confidential information or practices.
 - followed by a close-to-market, bilateral, confidential phase
Implementation in the farm, business. Confidentiality by the advisor, no need to disclose any confidential information to a third party.

D 2.1	Dissemination level PU-Public	70 / 81
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Collective research and advice

- Pre-competitive, preparatory, collective phase in a group to understand and learn the basics, principles of new methods, good practices, to carry out exercises, test new methods in general, see demonstrations, participate in learning communities/ learning from each other, co-creation (typical activities of Living Labs).
- Confidential, competitive phase: when the farmer, SFSC actor learned the basics from the collective phase, have a specific need for advice or an idea to be implemented in his business activities, bilateral consultations are carried out on-site or tests at the Living Lab.

Delivery methods of training of advisors

- Presentations, lessons
- Practical (group) exercises, case studies, problem-solving, role plays, brain-storming (LL)
- Reference to background information (best practice guides, inventories)
- Films, videos and other visual and audiovisual tools
- Demonstrations, practical trials (LL)
- Field, site visits
- The GAIN transition model, challenge labs (LL)
<https://www.smartchain-platform.eu/en/gain-model>
- Gamification

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Tools for the advisors to deliver advice

- The GAIN transition model, challenge labs (LL)
<https://www.smartchain-platform.eu/en/gain-model>
- Field, site visits
- Refer to best practice guides
- Films, videos and other visual and audiovisual tools
- Demonstrations, practical trials (LL)
- Collective research and advice,- small preparatory projects on a topic of joint interest to prepare the close-to-market phase using practical(group) exercises, case studies, problem-solving, role plays, pair – work brain-storming, comparisons.

(integrating input from the Rural Facilitator project 2021)

Collaboration with CoreNet

- Regular consultations and exchange of views to exploit complementarities and avoid duplication of work
- Initial contact COREnet to agree on the dates and methods of regular consultations. Assessing the matching of the WP3 conceptual framework with the needs, activities of CoreNet 21.07.2023
- The training needs of SFSC advisors 11.09.2023
- Prioritisation of the need for advice of SFSC actors and advisors' training needs 21.09.2023
- Design of the guidelines 21.10.2023
- Questions related to the M5 report 15.12.2023
- Questions related to the M6 report 18.03.2023

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ToDo's (1)

To Do's	Responsible	Deadline
Discuss, and agree on the conceptual framework Participation in online WP3 meeting	CBHU + all	14.07. 2023 11.-12.2023
Contact COREnet to agree on the dates and methods of regular consultations. Assess how to match the WP3 conceptual framework with the partners' and WPs' needs in CoreNet.	CBHU, INNO, KIS	21.07.2023
Define expected results and success criteria for the WP3 and the guidelines	all	21.07.2023
Concept to activate co-creation with advisors	AMP	31.08.2023
Identify the competence and potential training needs of SFSC advisors and advice for SFSC actors, including country-specific needs, and prepare a complete list	all	07.09.3023

ToDo's (2)

To Do's	Responsible	Deadline
Allocation of the work, subtasks, responsibilities, and deadlines for each step	CBHU, all	16.09.2023
Prioritise training needs and select topics. Allocate the development of the guidelines on different topics to different teams	all	16.09.2023
Designing the training guidelines for each selected topic: define the learning objectives, competency level, training methods, length, and initial table of content by the different teams teams	all	13.10.2023
Initial discussion of the design/ structure of the guidelines	all	20.10.2023

ToDo's (3)

To Do's	Responsible	Deadline
Organise a preparatory on-line meeting before the annual meeting	CBHU	16.-20.10. 2023
Review and adjustment of the design in the annual meeting	all	25.-27.10.2023
Elaborate on the milestone M5 report	CBHU, LL leaders	31.12.2023
Develop the first draft of the guidelines for each topic	all	15.03.2024
Discuss, and review the first draft	all	25.03.2024
Elaborate on the milestone M6 report	CBHU,ISEKI	31.03.2024

Deliverables and milestones

- D3.1 Validated guidelines and tools for SFSC-specific advice (CBHU, M58)
- M5 (T3.1) - Identification of SFSC needs in terms of advice (CBHU, M15) of SFSC needs (LL leaders)
 - Means of verification: Report (CBHU)
- M6 (T3.2) Draft guidelines and tools to be implemented at LL level CBHU, (M18)
 - Means of verification: Report with guidelines and testing protocols (CBHU)
- M4 Contribution (T2.3) 2nd and 3rd MAWs in LLs (M32,60)
 - Means of verification: Minutes of the MAWs (LL leaders)(KIS)

Contact

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5. Annex 5 Participants of the Focus Group Discussions

September 6, 2023

1. Rafal Serafin – Corenet, ISP
2. András Sebők - Campden BRI Hungary, EU4ADVICE
3. Yuna Chiffolleau – Corenet, INRAE
4. Zusepe Zidda – Corenet, Campagna Amica
5. Antonio Román Casas - Innogestiona Ambiental, EU4ADVICE
6. Branwen Miles - Copa-Cogeca, EU4ADVICE
7. Christian Jochum - Austrian Chamber of Agriculture, CORENET
8. Margaux Colombin - CTCPA, EU4ADVICE
9. Anne-Cécile Brit – INRAE
10. Ágnes Szegedyné Fricz - Corenet
11. Deborah Lettnerné - KIS
12. Edelbis López Dávila - UGENT, EU4ADVICE
13. Judith Molnár - Civitas, Corenet
14. Katalin Kujáni - KIS - moderator, EU4ADVICE
15. Ágnes Major - KIS, EU4ADVICE
16. Viktória Nagy - KIS, EU4ADVICE

September 11, 2023

1. Barbara Tocco - NCL, EU4ADVICE
2. Sarah Nolan - UCD, EU4ADVICE
3. Lucie Jeandrain - AMPED, EU4ADVICE
4. Mark Frederiks - AMPED, EU4ADVICE
5. Antonio Román Casas - Innogestiona Ambiental, EU4ADVICE
6. Juan Pablo - Innogestiona Ambiental, EU4ADVICE
7. Valentina Hazic - Croatia (not project partner)
8. Fedele Colantuono - University of Foggia, Corenet
9. Katalin Kujáni - KIS - moderator, EU4ADVICE
10. Ágnes Major - KIS, EU4ADVICE
11. Viktória Nagy - KIS, EU4ADVICE

D 2.1	Dissemination level PU-Public	76 / 81
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6. Annex 6 SLIDO poll results of the Focus Group Discussions

Focus group

06 - 12 Sep 2023

Poll results

slido

Open text poll

How do you imagine the perfect SFSC advisor? 1st focus group (1/3)

0 1 5

- Have direct contact with food producers, farmers and sfsc oragnizers/facilitators.
- - Awareness about producers needs
- Awareness about consumers needs - knowledge about local products that are requested by consumers in the local market - It should have excellent interpersonal skills to communicate and involve both producers and consumers -
- Knows territorial peculiarities, community dynamics, pedagogical skills, business-oriented and proactiva attitude
- Someone who is committed to improving the performance & impact of an SFSC over the long run with the interest/benefit to the farmers involved as a priority
- Close from the Farmers Good network that make it easy to contact the right people and find the right ressources
- a person able to listen, to facilitate but not impose, to make links with peers, to respect autonomy

slido

D 2.1	Dissemination level PU-Public	77 / 81
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Open text poll

How do you imagine the perfect SFSC advisor? 1st focus group

0 1 5

(2/3)

- the SFSC advisor is well-rounded, with perhaps more detailed expertise in a specific field for the business proposal for example
- Not knowing everything but able to forward each question to the right specialist Able to identify the most urgent needs regardless of the specific case Combining different fields of knowledge (legislation, funding, organisation, marketing)
- Someone who knows the market (business) in the region, the opportunities in terms of innovation, the regulations to best guide the project owner.
- open minded with strong basic knowledge,
- Someone with agriculture or economy background. Plus well communication skills
- a supportive, creative person who understands the main issues in the agriculture but also has knowledge on short food chains, opportunities, challenges
- Creative, solution-oriented, good communicator, experienced

slido

Open text poll

How do you imagine the perfect SFSC advisor? 1st focus group

0 1 5

(3/3)

- Good listener, good organiser, knowing agriculture
- Knows whom to ask

D 2.1	Dissemination level PU-Public	78 / 81
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Open text poll

What do you bring home from today's discussion? 1st focus group

009

(1/2)

- It was important to start this (overdue) conversation, which needs to challenge our assumptions about sfsc
- Many inputs for Next steps
- whilst advice needs to be tailored, this isn't always possible via training - but it is possible to give advisors the tools to tailor advice
- - It was good to see how advisory services are perceived from different perspectives - It was also interesting to look at the different criteria that advisory services should have
- Work more with the formal education program and system to introduce the topic of SFSC in the new young farmers and advisory services
- My "eggs" from today is that we have to think the issue broader and try to categorise the results. With the good participation between COREnet and EU4advice it was possible to have a broad discussion. Thanks!
- It was interactive, with the possibility of having the results of a

elido

Open text poll

What do you bring home from today's discussion? 1st focus group

009

(2/2)

supporting form. These results, with the questions asked, made it possible to debate and for each country to express its views on the level of progress made on these subjects! Thank you very much!

- Countries are very diverse, we must consider and respond accordingly
- A lot of questions..., energy..., ideas. Thanks!

D 2.1	Dissemination level PU-Public	79 / 81
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Open text poll

How do you imagine the perfect SFSC advisor? 2nd focus group

008

- Knowledgeable, pro-active, good listener, emphatic, trusted
- Understanding the farmers and their position, ability to solve the conflicts
- Open to networking, always updated about innovation and pioneer for new possibilities to propose to farmers offering them opportunities
- Strong connections and wide network, trusted within the community, practical experience of SFSCs, regenerative focus
- Open minded, knowledge of food chains
- Have strong connection to the region/territory
- Transparent, fair, regenerative
- Large network Open for collaboration Aware of all systemic barriers of the food system Worked on all archetypes of sfsc

slido

D 2.1	Dissemination level PU-Public	80 / 81
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Open text poll

What do you bring home from today's discussion? 2nd focus group

006

(1/2)

- Advisory system should be diverse in terms of actors and topics
- Trust is essential for being a 'good' advisor, but even more so in context of SFSCs. For SFSCs a lot of advisors' attributes relate to intangible/ subjective measures..
- The challenge of quantifying and measuring SFSC advisor qualities; The opportunities for including a wide range of individuals and skill sets as advisors (younger generation, previous experience in conversational agri.. etc); The need for trust and community networks for SFSC advice
- Importance of network, nobody is excluded and everyone represent a resource for knowledge and experience sharing
- Lots of alignment in thinking despite being from lots of different countries in the EU - even more reasons to connect SFSC (advisors) further 😊
- Initiatives need more trust

Open text poll

What do you bring home from today's discussion? 2nd focus group

006

(2/2)

than money 😊

D 2.1	Dissemination level PU-Public	81 / 81
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